

1989

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8/2278

BLAF

Relationship of rice embryo weight and salinity tolerance at seedling stage

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We screened 19 indica and 6 japonica cultivars with varying embryo weights for salt tolerance, using water culture in the IRRI phytotron glasshouse (29/21 °C (day/night) temperature, 70% relative humidity, natural daylight). Salinity stress of 6800 ppm (EC 12 dS/m) was introduced by adding 1:1 mixture of NaCl and CaCl₂ to the nutrient solution. Seedling survival after 2 wk salinization was taken as the criterion for salt tolerance.

Embryo weight/50 seeds ranged from 0.0140 g (Intan Gawri and Palman 46)

to 0.0467 g (Rikuto Norin 15). Seedling survival under salinity stress ranged from 2 (Palman 46) to 90 (IR51491-AC4-6).

Among the cultivars studied, the association between embryo weight and salt tolerance was not significant ($r = 0.2151$) (see table). This finding does not support earlier reports of such an association. □

IRRN 14:3 (June 1989)

Correlation ($r = 0.2151^{ns}$) between embryo weight and seedling survival after 14 d salinization (EC = 12 dS/m). IRRI, 1989.

Cultivar	Embryo weight (g)	Survival (%)
Rikuto Norin 15	0.0467	7
Bombilla	0.0454	36
Chang You Zae Rae	0.0450	10
Thatnosubnet	0.0440	12
Jinbu 4	0.0393	45
Pokkali	0.0386	85
Nona Bokra	0.0358	89
IR51491-AC4-6	0.0309	90
IR31779-19-3-3-2-2	0.0302	10
RNR1429	0.0299	18
IR51491-AC4-7	0.0297	82
IR51500-AC9-8	0.0272	32
TNAU (AD) 103	0.0263	8
MI-48	0.0245	2
Khao youth	0.0237	22
IR25924-92-1-3	0.0236	5
Laxmi	0.0227	8
IR28	0.0226	20
Suweon 341	0.0219	70
IR36	0.0209	42
NIAB6	0.0208	25
Duansan	0.0202	18
Basmati 370	0.0195	20
Intan Gawri	0.0140	8
Palman 46	0.0140	2